
Ownership Patterns in Shaping Management Practices of Private Radio Stations in Nigeria

Joyce Dan-Matthew; Prof. Anthony Iorver Igyuve & Prof. Muhammad Sani Rabi

Department of Communication
Nasarawa State University, Keffi, Nigeria
krisiel02@gmail.com +2348036009466

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15874496>

Abstract

The deregulation of the broadcast sector in 1992 has influenced the ownership structures in radio ownership patterns in Nigeria. These structures emerged in the form of political, religious, corporate and individual, thereby shaping radio's operation and content delivery. This study explored the relationship between ownership patterns and the management practices employed by private radio stations in Nigeria. Using the political economy media theory and agency theory, the conceptual study posited that the nature of ownership, whether individual, corporate, religious or politically affiliated, significantly influences operational strategies, programming decisions, financial management. The researchers further observed that ownership influences not only operational efficiency, but also the ideological orientation of media output, impact station autonomy, revenue generation strategies, adherence to professional journalism standards and affects public trust and journalistic independence.

Keywords: Ownership Patterns, Management Practices, Media Management, Organisational Culture, Editorial Independence, Private Radio Stations, Nigeria